

HUJAYRANING REJALASHTIRILGAN O'LIMI APOPTOZ

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda hujayralarning rejalashtirilgan o'limi haqida. Apoptoz – bu keraksiz hujayraning tarkibiy qismlari immun hujayralar tomonidan “yig‘ish” uchun mayda membrana qadoqlariga o‘raladigan tartibli jarayon. Apoptoz rivojlanish jarayonida (ortiqcha) hujayralarni yo‘q qilish, xavf tug‘dirishi mumkin bo‘lgan saraton va virus bilan infeksiyalangan hujayralardan organizmni tozalash va odam tanasida muvozanatni ta‘minlash vazifasini bajaradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Apoptoz, virus, saraton, infeksiya, immun, makrofag, oqsil, prokaspaza,

Kirish Apoptoz- bu tartibli programmashtirilgan hujayra o‘limining bir turi. Apoptoz natijasida hujayra apoptotik tanachalarga bo‘linib ketadi. Apoptotik tanachalar esa tezda (o‘rtacha 90 minut) makrofaglar yoki qo‘shni hujayralar tomonidan yallig‘lanishga yol qoymay yutib olinadilar. Ko‘p hujayrali organizmda apoptoz ikki yo‘l bilan vujudga kelishi mumkin:

1) Tashqi signallar bo‘ylab. 2) Mitoxondriyaviy signal yo‘l orqali.

Umurtqali organizmlarda mitoxondriyaviy signal yo‘l orqali bo‘lib o‘tadigan programmashtirilgan hujayra o‘limi ko‘proq uchraydi.

Apoptozning mitoxondriyaviy signal yo‘li hujayra sitoplazmasiga apoptogen oqsillarning chiqishi natijasida bo‘lib o‘tadi. Bu ikkita sababdan kelib chiqishi mumkin: 1. mitoxondriyaning membranalari yorilishi va 2. mitoxondriya membranalarining o‘tkazuvchanligini oshib ketishi natijasida.

Mitoxondriya membranalarining o‘tkazuvchanligi oshishida apoptotik Bcl-2-oqsillar (Bax va Bak oqsillari) katta ahamiyatga ega. Bcl-2-oqsillar mitoxondriya membranalariga o‘tirib sitoplazmaga apoptozda ishtirok etadigan oqsillarni – sitoxrom c, prokaspaza va AIF-flavoproteainlar - chiqib ketishini ta‘minlab beradi.

Sitoplazmada sitoxrom c [APAF-1](#) oqsili bilan apoptosoma degan organellani hosil qilishda ishtirok etadi. APAF-1 va sitoxrom c ga prokaspaza-9 oqsili qo‘shilib yetuk apoptosomani hosil qiladi. Apoptosoma sitoplazmadagi kaspaza -9 oqsillarni topib, ularni prokaspaza-3 oqsillari bilan qoshadi va apoptozda ishtirok etadigan tayyor kaspaza-3 oqsilini hosil qiladi. AIF-flavoproteini kaspaza va prokaspaza oqsillaridan alohida apoptozda ishtirok etadi. Kaspaza-9 hujayra sitoplazmasida kaspazalar kaskadini hosil qiladi. Kaspazalarning asosiy vazifasi hujayrada joylashgan hamma organoidlarni parchalash bilan bo‘g‘liq. Kaspazalar yadro membranalarini, sitoskelet oqsillarini, hujayralar o‘rtasidagi bo‘lgan birikishlarni buzilishida ishtirok etadi.

Viruslar, bir qancha bakteriya va zamburug'larning hujayra ichi parazitlari hisoblanadi. Hayvon va odam organizmida bularga nisbatan maxsus antitelolar ishlab chiqsa ham, ular sitoplazmaga joylashib olgan parazitlarni oxirigacha yo'q qilolmaydi. Shundan so'ng sitotoksik T-limfositlar o'z ta'sirini o'tkaza boshlaydi. Bular infeksiya qo'zg'atuvchilar bilan zararlangan hujayralarni yo'q qiladi, shu orqali ularning kelgusida ko'payishini to'xtatadi. T-killer sog' hujayralar orasidan zararlangan hujayralarni tanib oladi va bu nishon hujayrani o'limi haqidagi dasturi ishga solib uni halok qilad. Tabiiy killerlar apoptoz mexanizmi bo'yicha o'sma chaqiruvchi hujayralarni ham yo'q qilishi mumkin.

Apoptoz va virusli infeksiya: virusli gepatit paytida kuzatiladi, jigarda kaunsilman hujayralari bilan birga apoptik hujayra fragmentlari ham uchraydi. Apoptoz yo'li bilan katta bo'lmagan do'zalarda ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi va nekrozni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin bo'lgan zararlovchi omillar bilan zararlangan hujayralar ham yo'q qilinadi. Masalan: yuqori temperature, ionlavchi nurlanish, o'smaga qarshi dori-darmonlar natijasida. Hujayralar apoptik o'limning farqli tomonlari, bu yallig'lanish reaksiyalari bo'lmasligi va jarayonning chegaralanganligidandir. Apoptoz paytida o'layotgan hujayra qo'shni hujayralarni zararlanishi oldini olish shuning uchun apoptozni hujayraviy altruizm- qo'shni hujayralar uchun o'z-o'zini halok qilish deyish mumkin.

Xulosa. Bugungi kunda hujayralarning rejalashtirilgan o'limi to'liqligicha o'rganilmagan. Shu bois turli xil ishlar olib borilmoqda. Hujayralarning ortiqcha qoldiqlaridan tozalash uchun apoptoz va makrofaglar ishlatiladi.

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